

Will Tesla capitalize on its first-mover advantage in modular architecture?

Ecology, new vehicle architecture, and a new business model — all converge at a single point in the future.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19101831>

At one time, Tesla changed the vector of development of the global automotive industry, which led to the emergence of new fast-growing technology companies, and the old manufacturers changed their strategies. The main aspects of Tesla's influence on the automotive industry :

- The development of electric car philosophy. Proving its viability and advantages over classic cars.
- Innovations in technology and components - battery technology, Supercharger fast charging networks, over-the-air (OTA) updates, the trend towards minimalism in the interior.
- Development of autopilot and FSD (I discussed this in more detail in another article).
- Revolutionary technologies in production - Unboxed Process and Gigacasting.
- Changes in the business model - direct sales without dealers, changes in service.

Tesla's core foundation is its innovative approach to all aspects of its operations. However, competitors are constantly breathing down its neck and outflanking it.

Innovations eventually come to an end, the hype around new technologies fades, and quick returns fade. And then comes the hard, tedious work of working in a competitive market. Under these circumstances, it becomes vital for a company to avoid mistakes in its philosophy and strategy for applying innovative technologies.

So is Tesla moving in the right direction in terms of innovation as a car manufacturer?

Next, I will look at some of the technologies that Tesla is relying on to maintain its leadership in the auto industry and **offer my solutions to the problems identified.**

So, let's start with the Gigacasting technology that Tesla used in 2020. The rear floor of the Model Y, which previously consisted of 70 individual parts, was replaced with just one massive aluminum casting.

Tesla later applied this technology to the front and rear body panels of some of its models.

Gigacasting is the production of enormous, single-piece body parts using giant high-pressure casting machines.

I won't go into the technical details of this technology; I'll only point out the positive and negative aspects that have emerged over the years of using it. **For consumers**, the positive aspects are:

- Weight reduction and energy efficiency, as aluminum casting is lighter than steel structures, which is important for the electric vehicle's range.
- Precision and Rigidity – Gigacasting is stronger and more precise in geometry. This improves handling and crash safety.
- Durability - aluminum casting is virtually impervious to corrosion.
- Less creaking and fatigue deformation.

Disadvantages:

- **Poor repairability is the main problem.** If a Gigacast part is damaged in an accident, it is nearly impossible to repair. The introduction of crumple zones does not fundamentally solve this problem. The labor intensity, complexity, and cost of body repair exceeds that of comparable repairs on welded bodies. Complete replacement of a Gigacast part can take 60 standard hours or more. Special structural adhesives and rivets are used when assembling such components, making such repairs problematic unless performed by authorized service centers. As a result, the car often ends up being written off as a total loss due to the economic impracticality of repair.
- **Increased insurance costs** (Full coverage) due to repairability and scrappage rates. Gigacasting increases insurance costs by an average of 15–30% compared to similar vehicles assembled using traditional methods, but in certain markets this figure can exceed 40%.
- Due to the high rigidity of the body, tire wear increases (about 10%).

What are the positive aspects for the manufacturer:

- Radical simplification of production - one machine replaces hundreds of welding robots.
- Space saving - the factory area is reduced by 30-40% as giant welding lines are no longer needed.
- The body assembly time is significantly reduced.
- **Significant reduction in cost and increase in marginality.**

The high cost of Gigacasting equipment may be considered a negative aspect for the manufacturer, but the positive aspects of the technology compensate for this drawback.

The second technology Tesla is betting on is the Unboxed Process. Tesla is implementing it for its cheapest electric car and robotaxis, the Cybercab.

This technology is designed to replace the classic conveyor-belt assembly of cars with a **modular system**, where several large modules are **assembled in parallel** and joined at the finish line.

The main advantage of this technology **is reduced production costs**, and this benefit is primarily intended for the manufacturer. **The consumer faces almost the same disadvantages** as with Gigacasting technology, and even more so.

The way Tesla presents this technology, **it's essentially a "disposable car" concept**. For the manufacturer, modularity is about quick assembly, not repairability.

In the Unboxed Process architecture, modules are virtually impossible to replace as a whole due to their permanent connection (glued and riveted assembly), and the non-detachable modular construction makes conventional repairs challenging. **This is the main problem of the new production model.**

This architecture treats **the car as a gadget**. It is cost-effective to operate during the warranty period, but thereafter, it requires expensive insurance to cover potential breakdowns or total loss.

The producer gets mass production, and the consumer gets a low initial purchase price. **And economically, this scheme will be viable only in conjunction with the manufacturer -insurance company -consumer.**

These two new technologies, Gigacasting and Unboxed Process, are **united by the desire for a modular architecture**. And my opinion is that **this architecture is the future of the automotive industry.**

In my articles, I described the concept of modular architecture. And one of the main fundamental parameters there was **environmental friendliness (in the full life cycle - production, operation, disposal), quality and speed of service for the consumer**. And for uncompromising provision of these three qualities, modular architecture (as the basis) is best suited.

Do the new Tesla technologies (Gigacasting and Unboxed Process) meet the criteria of environmental friendliness, quality and speed of service for the consumer? Obviously not.

These technologies, in their current form, primarily benefit Tesla itself, reducing the cost of cars and increasing the speed of production processes.

For the consumer, the initial low purchase price results in an increase in the final cost of ownership due to insurance, which now has to cover repairs not only in the event of an accident, but also in some cases of routine repairs.

The repair time increases and the number of places where this repair can be carried out efficiently decreases. Also, the price of selling a used car may be lower than expected due to the small number of people willing to deal with a car with poor repairability and complexity of repair, high insurance costs, and possible hidden faults that would make it advisable to scrap the car.

As a result, **consumers become hostage to their cars' poor repairability**. This leads to the following conclusion: **their vehicles are not compliant with future environmental requirements**.

And here we need to elaborate. Today, the primary focus of environmental initiatives is decarbonization, which means eliminating hydrocarbon combustion and reducing the carbon footprint, as well as implementing a circular economy, which entails waste minimization and responsible consumption.

And while Tesla is doing well with its hydrocarbon combustion, it's not quite as good with other aspects of environmental sustainability.

Tesla is undoubtedly implementing green technologies in its production, among which one can note the transition to LFP (lithium iron phosphate) batteries, which are considered environmentally friendly, trying to implement a closed-loop battery recycling system and other smaller initiatives. **But low reparability and the "disposable car" architecture will prevent Tesla from becoming the green company of the future. The problem lies in the carbon footprint of production and disposal.**

For electric vehicles, this can account for 50-70% of the total carbon footprint of the vehicle's life cycle. For gasoline-powered vehicles, this figure averages 35%—and this shows **the environmental impact of production itself.**

If a car with good reparability indicators can be used for 15 years, then a car with poor reparability will last for half as long, and in 15 years, two such cars will need to be produced, and their combined carbon footprint, related to production and disposal, will double.

Therefore, **the shorter a car's life cycle, the higher its carbon footprint and negative impact on the environment.** And no recycling technologies will make a significant difference.

In the scheme of shortening the life cycle of a car, the environment is the first to lose, then the consumer, while the manufacturer and, to some extent, insurance companies are the winners.

And this loophole can be in effect for a very long time, until the life cycle of the car is regulated at the legislative level.

What can be done to eliminate the problems described above? It is obvious that the non-removable connection of modules and their non-maintainability is a dead end not only in the context of ecology.

The car of the future, based on a modular architecture, will have a permanent life cycle — the car will be completely disposed of only in case of complete destruction, its modular topology will be modified, updating individual modules as they fail due to the impossibility of repair and obsolescence.

It is obvious that modules of this architecture **must have maximum maintainability, turning from a Black box into a White box.**

Also, all connections between modules must be detachable and capable of robotic manipulation for connection/disconnection, while having the same structural strength and reliability as when connecting modern Gigacasting parts.

This can be achieved by changing the joining technology. These could include special release elements, such as local heating elements built into the part during the casting process to alter the aggregation state of a new type of structural adhesive.

Special reusable rivets or other fastening elements could also be developed. **And disassembling and assembling such modules should take minutes, not hours or days.**

Gigacasting technology deserves special mention. By pioneering this technology, **Tesla opened a new chapter in the history of the global automotive industry, paving the way for modular architecture.** In the future, the entire car body will be composed of components produced using this technology.

Nowadays, body repairs on classic welded cars after serious accidents **can take weeks or months.**

This time includes defect detection, disassembly, ordering spare parts, the repair itself, assembly, and various logistical and technological delays. At the same time, **the quality of such repairs** is very dependent on the human factor and **is often unsatisfactory.**

With a fully modular design (modules can be separated and reassembled in minutes), body repairs **would take hours or even days.** The car would be disassembled down to the individual body parts to be replaced, like a LEGO set.

In the future, we expect a restructuring of the service business model toward consolidation of repair stations. Instead of 100 small repair and maintenance stations, **there will be one Mega-Service Station** in a specific location, for example, in each state.

At such a Mega-Service Station, the removed damaged body part will be remelted into a new one on-site. **This repair method will be cost-effective and environmentally friendly, even for minor body damage.**

Giga-casting equipment will be improved to reduce costs and increase versatility (the ability to cast parts of any configuration on a single piece of equipment).

As a result, the manufacturer will receive a new business model of concentrating the entire life cycle of a car in one hand as compensation for the reduction in production and sales of new cars due to environmental requirements.

Where is Tesla heading as an automotive company now, having set a new direction with its modular architecture? **Perhaps Tesla is currently at an intermediate point, testing new technologies and correcting its mistakes.** Whether it will maintain its leadership in innovation or join the ranks of an average automotive company—time will tell.

In the next article, I will look at other Tesla technology solutions, including battery and charging technologies.